

ON THE INTERACTION OF ARABIC ACID WITH BASES

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Arabic acid, prepared and purified by different methods, has been titrated by potentiometric and conductometric methods with different bases having monovalent and divalent cations. The potentiometric titration curves present the characteristics of strong monobasic acids, while the conductometric ones yield two inflexions, one corresponding to the neutralisation of the free acidity and the other, to the total acidity. Different bases show different total acidities but the total acidities for the same base by the potentiometric and conductometric methods agree with each other. The equivalent weight of the acid by titration with NaOH amounts to 1190.

In previous communications on the properties of arabic acid solutions (this *Journal* 1949, 26, 81, 151) the mode of variation of physical and electrochemical properties with concentration was studied. The results obtained therein tend to the conclusions that there is formation of aggregates in this system and the process appears to be progressive from very low concentrations and that there appears to be no evidence of the existence of any critical concentration. In the present communication interaction of this acid with different bases has been studied both by E.M.F. and by conductometric methods with a view to studying how this acid reacts with the commoner bases, *i.e.* the shape of the titration curves, number of inflexion points, total acidities etc.

EXPERIMENTAL

Four different bases having monovalent and bivalent cations *viz.*, NaOH, KOH, Ba(OH)₂ and Ca(OH)₂, were used in this connection. The substances were all of Merck's reagent quality dissolved in equilibrium water of specific conductance 1.2×10^{-6} mho at 35°. Three different specimens of arabic acid solutions were used: Sol U prepared according to the method of Bungenberg de Jong (*Koll. Chem.-Beih.*, 1938, 47, 254) without electro dialysis; sol E, prepared by further purification of sol U by electro dialysis; and sol T prepared by direct electro dialysis of gum arabic according to the procedure followed by Thomas and Murray (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1928, 32, 676).

Potentiometric measurements were carried out with the help of a K-type potentiometer (Leeds and Northrup) reading up to 0.05 millivolts and specific conductance was measured with an L and N bridge and an induction coil having a frequency of about 1000 cycles/sec. All measurements refer to a temperature of $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$. Hydrogen electrode was used with its usual precautions (*cf.* Mukherjee and co-workers, *Indian J. Agric. Sci.*, 1936, 6, 517). Hydrogen gas was generated by electrolysis of 15% NaOH solution between nickel electrodes. Although there was a slight tendency on the part of the solution to froth due to bubbling of hydrogen, this, when controlled by regulating the bubbling of the gas, caused no inconvenience to work with, nor any loss of accuracy, as evident from the close agreement between the p_H measurements by hydrogen and quinhydrone electrodes side by side in the same solution (*vide* Table I). Reproducibility of potentiometric measurements was tested by titrating the same sol twice with NaOH and

found to be satisfactory because the two titration curves overlapped almost over their entire course.

TABLE I

 p_H values

Pt-H ₂ electrode	2.86	3.44	3.81	4.02
Quinhydrone electrode	2.93	3.41	3.84	4.10

The question of attainment of equilibrium after addition of each instalment of the bases was studied by bottle titrations as referred to in a previous paper by one of the authors (Mukherjee and Ghosh, *loc. cit.*) from which it appears that the reaction of the acid with the base attains completion almost immediately. Results of the measurements appear in the next section.

DISCUSSION

Potentiometric Study

Inflexion Points.—Specimens of potentiometric titration curves have been shown in Fig. 1. All the four bases were tried with sol U but sols E and T were examined with NaOH and Ba(OH)₂ only. The curves all present the characteristic features of a strong monobasic acid with a clear and sharp inflexion in the neighbourhood of p_H 7. The initial flat (or buffer) portion runs to a higher concentration of the base in the case of Ca(OH)₂ than with all other bases. The buffer index curves drawn by plotting $\Delta b/\Delta p_H$ (where b is the amount of the base added and Δb is the base required to change the pH of the solution by unity) have been found to show only one minimum.

FIG. 1

Total Acidity.—The total acidities calculated from the end-point of the titration ($p_n, 7$) are different for the different bases. With sol U, where all the four bases were studied $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ showed the highest total acidity and the others show lower values in the order; $\text{Ca} > \text{Ba} > \text{K} > \text{Na}$. With sols E and T, the bivalent cation Ba always showed a higher value than Na. The data have been shown in Table II.

TABLE II

Temp. = $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$

Soln.	Base.	Total acidity*	Soln.	Base.	Total acidity*
Sol U	NaOH	76.0	Sol E	NaOH	80.0
	KOH	80.5		$\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$	93.0
	$\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$	83.5	Sol T	NaOH	75.0
	$\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$	89.5		$\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$	84

*Total acidity is expressed in terms of milli-equivalents of the base per 10 g of the acid.

The observed differences in total acidities are not, however, very much marked compared to those observed by Mukherjee and co-workers (vide extensive work of J. N. Mukherjee and co-workers published in the *J. Agric. Sci.*, 1935-1943) in the case of hydrogen clays and hydrogen bentonite suspensions. But such differences in total acidities were not observed by previous workers (cf. Thomas and Murray, *loc. cit.*, Pauli and Palmrich, *Kolloid Z.*, 1937, 79, 63) in their potentiometric titrations with this gum acid. A slight difference was observed only in the conductometric titrations with NaOH and $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$ by Pauli and Palmrich (*loc. cit.*).

Although the total acidity changes with the nature of the bases used for the interaction, the concentration of the solution appears to have no influence as reported by the authors in a previous communication (Mukherjee *et al.*, *loc. cit.*). In the present case all titrations were carried out with 1% solutions. Thus, it may be inferred that though there is aggregate formation proceeding in this system with increasing concentration, it does not interfere with the total acidity, *i.e.* the COOH groups remain always readily available to the base for interaction.

Potentiometric titration curves for the ultrafiltrate by cello membranes (No. 600) also resemble those of the parent sols but the total acidities are less. The relevant results for the ultrafiltrate appear graphically in Fig. 2. Although the difference between the mono- and bivalent cations persists in the ultrafiltrate, it is definitely less than that observed in the case of the parent sol.

It appears that the difference in the total acidities with different bases may be due to the different base exchange capacities of the different cations present. It is thus due to a surface interaction and is expected to be quite marked where the surface is large *i.e.*, in cases where micelles are formed by aggregation of the monomers. In the light of these considerations the ultrafiltrate also appears to contain micelles like its parent sol and since the difference between the different bases is smaller than in the latter, the micelles are also likely to be smaller or fewer.

Fig. 2

Conductometric Study

Inflexions.— Conductometric titration curves* (Fig. 3) show two inflexion points. Apparently the acid appears dibasic (in contrast with the potentiometric titration curves where the monobasic character is prominently brought out). On closer examination it was noticed that the first inflexion points for the different bases were practically coincident and that they roughly tallied with the neutralisation of the free acidity or the hydrogen-ion activity of the solution (Table III).

TABLE III

Sol conc.	Base used.	a_H from $p^H \times 10^4$.	Base at first inflexion $\times 10^4 N$.	Base at 2nd inflex. Total acidity/100 g.
Sol U (0.98%)	NaOH	11.96	13.1	76.0
	KOH	—	13.2	81.0
	Ba(OH) ₂	—	16.8	85.0
	Ca(OH) ₂	—	16.0	92.0
Sol E (1.10%)	NaOH	17.1	19.0	76.0
	Ba(OH) ₂	—	24.0	90.0

*Conductometric titrations were carried out with sols U and E only and not with sol T since results of conductometric titration of solutions prepared in the same method as sol T already appear in the literature (cf. Thomas and Murray, *loc. cit.* Pauli and Palmrich, *loc. cit.*).

The first inflexion, as evident from the table above, does not occur at exactly half the amount of the base required for the second inflexion. This is probably further suggestive of the fact that the acid is not probably a dibasic one, but that the first inflexion indicates the neutralisation of the hydrogen-ion activity of the solution. Beyond this, however, the interaction of the acid with the base presents the features of the neutralisation of weak acids and probably depends on the availability of hydrogen ions by dissociation of the acid which appears to be a slow process.

Fig. 3

The second inflexion is quite sharp and probably marks the total neutralisation of the acid and the last portion of the titration curve resembles the alkali line in ordinary conductometric titrations. One interesting feature that emerges from these curves is that in the case of interaction of the acid with KOH the specific conductance at the second inflexion exceeds that of the pure solution which is not observed in the case of other bases. Potassium thus behaves slightly differently towards this acid and from the other cations. The reason for this is not quite clear.

Total Acidity.—Total acidities by this method tally with those by the potentiometric titrations and the cationic order also runs as before. The total acidity of the arabic acid is thus not a definite quantity but depends on the nature of the base used for titration. Though a small difference was observed in the total acidities in their conductometric titration of this acid with NaOH and Ba(OH)₂, Pauli and Palmrich (*loc. cit.*) did not take any serious notice of this. The difference although small is definite because in a large number of conductometric titrations, which were carried out in course of these and other investigations in these laboratories, a difference of approximately the same magnitude was always observed. This aspect will be taken up again in connection with the interaction of this acid with neutral salts having cations of different valencies in the next

communication on this subject. The equivalent weight of the acid calculated from the second inflexion point with NaOH amounts to about 1190.

C O N C L U S I O N

Potentiometric titration curves of arabic acid solutions present the characteristics of a strong monobasic acid.

Conductometric titration curves apparently present the characters of a dibasic acid in showing two inflexions in their course. The first of these, however, coincides with the neutralisation of the hydrogen-ion activity or the free acidity of the solution and occurs at the same point for the different bases used for titration. The second inflexion with different bases probably corresponds to the neutralisation of the acid and gives the total acidity.

Total acidities obtained by neutralisation of the acid by both potentiometric and conductometric methods are different and vary in the order : $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2 > \text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2 > \text{KOH} > \text{NaOH}$.

Total acidities by the potentiometric and conductometric methods agree with each other for the different bases used. The equivalent weight of the acid, calculated on the basis of titration with NaOH, amounts to 1190 approximately.

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